

EDAP+ TN on Vodafone Atmospheric Data Assessment Validation

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	05/07/2024	First version
2.0	22/11/2024	Addressing minor comments from Vodafone International

REFERENCE

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. Webpage of Sentec, the weather sensors producer: <https://cdsentec.com/>
- RD-2. Webpage of Kunak air, the air quality sensors producer: <https://kunakair.com/>
- RD-3. Global Integrated Surface Database ISD - [Global Hourly - Integrated Surface Database \(ISD\) | National Centers for Environmental Information \(NCEI\) \(noaa.gov\)](https://www.noaa.gov/global-hourly-integrated-surface-database)
- RD-4. Spanish State Meteorological Agency AEMET - [AEMET OpenData - State Meteorological Agency - AEMET - Spanish Government](https://www.aemet.es)
- RD-5. Air quality data from UK-air network. URL: https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/data_selector_service?show=auto&submit=Reset&f_limit_was=1
- RD-6. NASA Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) Version 07 Technical note, https://arthurhou.pps.eosdis.nasa.gov/Documents/IMERG_TechnicalDocumentation_final.pdf
- RD-7. Product User Manual (PUM) for product H60B, H63/P-IN-SEVIRI-PMW, P-IN-SEVIRI_E Precipitation rate at ground by GEO/IR supported by LEO/MW, <https://hsaf.meteoam.it/Products/Detail?prod=H60B>
- RD-8. EDAP+ Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework - Atmospheric Guidelines. <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/Atmospheric+Mission+Quality+Assessment+Guidelines.pdf/7d698d9e-fe05-7ec3-7565-4d933f34e85b>
- RD-9. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.1, 31st October 2021.
- RD-10. Federal climate complex data documentation for integrated Surface Data (ISD). URL: <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/global-hourly/doc/isd-format-document.pdf>
- RD-11. Help document related to the ISD data for CSV format. URL: https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/global-hourly/doc/CSV_HELP.pdf
- RD-12. Lawrence, M. G. (2005). The relationship between relative humidity and the dewpoint temperature in moist air: A simple conversion and applications. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 86(2), 225-234. URL: <https://climate.envsci.rutgers.edu/pdf/LawrenceRHdewpointBAMS.pdf>
- RD-13. Sea level pressure derivation algorithm: <https://blog.mensor.com/blog/adjusting-barometric-pressure-readings-for-aviation-and-meteorology>
- RD-14. Lee, J. C. Y., Fields, M. J., and Lundquist, J. K.: Assessing variability of wind speed: comparison and validation of 27 methodologies, *Wind Energ. Sci.*, 3, 845–868, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-3-845-2018>, 2018.
- RD-15. Freedman, D., Pisani, R., & Purves, R. (2007). *Statistics* (international student edition). Pisani, R. Purves, 4th Edn. WW Norton & Company, New York.
- RD-16. Wilk, M. B., & Gnanadesikan, R. (1968). Probability plotting methods for the analysis for the analysis of data. *Biometrika*, 55(1), 1-17.
- RD-17. Local air quality Management. Technical guidance (TG16), Part IV of the environment Act 1995 – Environment (Northern Ireland) Order 2002 part III. Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs. April 2016. URL: <https://www.scottishairquality.scot/assets/documents/laqm-tg16-april-16-v1.pdf>
- RD-18. UK-air Air quality network sensors certificate of calibration. Ricardo Energy and Environment. URL:

https://www.scottishairquality.scot/sites/default/files/orig/assets/ukas-certs/Glasgow_6202.pdf

RD-19. Huffman, G.J., E.F. Stocker, D.T. Bolvin, E.J. Nelkin, Jackson Tan (2023), GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly 0.1 degree x 0.1 degree V07, Greenbelt, MD, Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC), Accessed: [01/04/2024], [10.5067/GPM/IMERG/3B-HH/07](https://doi.org/10.5067/GPM/IMERG/3B-HH/07)

RD-20. NASA Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) Version 07
https://arthurhou.pps.eosdis.nasa.gov/Documents/IMERG_V07_ATBD_final.pdf

RD-21. Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document (ATBD) for product H60 P-IN-SEVIRI-PMW, H63 P-IN-SEVIRI-PMW_E Precipitation rate at ground by GEO/IR supported by LEO/MW - SAF/HSAF/ATBD-60-63.

GLOSSARY

ISD: Integrated Surface Dataset

NOAA: National Centers for Environmental Information

AEMET: Agencia Estatal de Meteorología

PCC: Pearson's Correlation Coefficient

K2: sensor K-A3 KUNAK 2

K4: sensor K-A3 KUNAK 4

GPM: GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly 0.1 degree x 0.1 degree V07

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the technical assessment of Vodafone's pilot project "*Vodafone Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor*". The project is composed of three distinct kinds of atmospheric products:

- meteorological stations (hosted on passive telecoms infrastructure, Vantage Towers),
- air quality ground-based sensors,
- precipitation intensity retrieval from wireless links (virtual rain gauges).

The pilot project is started in 2022, comprising different test phases.

Meteorological stations are produced by SENTEC and perform direct measurements of atmospheric parameters (temperature, pressure, relative humidity etc.) [RD-1] and were installed across Spain.

Air quality sensors are produced by KUNAK AIR and perform direct measurements of oxides concentrations (carbon dioxide, nitric oxide, etc.) and particulate matters (PM 1, 2.5 etc.) [RD-2]. The complete list of air quality sensors parameters is summarized in Table 5.1. Air quality sensors were installed in Glasgow city.

The produced data are ground based, obtained from network of sensors or in the case of precipitation intensity retrieved from wireless links of Vodafone's infrastructure (antennas-antennas 5G signals). The rain intensity retrieval has been performed by Wireless DNA. The scope of the project is to use the Vodafone's infrastructure to mount the sensors and provide environmental data service. This infrastructure can deliver real-time data high resolution in space and time broad spatial coverage (more than 140K sites). Figure 1-1 shows the countries, across Europe and Africa, potentially involved into the project.

Figure 1-1 Map of Nations potentially involved in the Vodafone *Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor* project.

For meteorological and air quality data, the intercomparison exercises are produced with local networks of stations measuring the same atmospheric parameters. Data was cross-referenced with adjacent stations/sensors when there was no reference available in the proximity. Global Integrated Surface Database ISD, [RD-3], and daily means data from Spanish State Meteorological Agency AEMET, [RD-4], has been used to compare the meteorological products, while air quality data has been compared with UK-air air quality network data, [RD-5].

Precipitation intensity dataset is composed by more than 8 million observations located in the east Spain coast during the period between 18th May and 3rd June 2023. The dataset has been compared with two different satellite products containing precipitation data acquired from geostationary satellites and low earth orbit microwave observations, from NASA GPM [RD-6] and Eumetsat SEVIRI [RD-7]. Unfortunately, no ground measurements were available for the intercomparison.

Three separated chapters are presented, one for each product type. The maturity matrix here presented is a modified version of original one since the original scope is the assessment of satellite missions. The maturity matrix and validation comprise the three products: weather, air quality and precipitation data.

1.1 Main Results

The results show that data from meteorological stations are reliable, as their measurements align with those of the reference stations within the margin of error. Statistical analyses across various sites point out a positive correlation and high consistency. The air quality product assessment indicates that there is significant room for improvement, especially regarding sensors' calibration and data filtering.

The meteorological, air quality network and precipitation data that uses Vodafone's ground infrastructure for sensor installation, or related to the 5G transmissions provides extensive territorial coverage and holds significant potential. This results in a large volume of atmospheric data that could be ingested in global networks and used for atmospheric and climate modelling applications.

Regarding the precipitation data, the lack of detailed information on the retrieval/calibration algorithm, the lack of uncertainty and other data characterizing information makes difficult to establish the quality of the measurements. The intercomparison exercises produces a basic agreement, with the better results obtained in the comparison of average precipitation rate map or averaged time series of the region, but low correlation coefficient in the one-to-one measurements comparison. These results could be ascribed to the very local and stochastic nature of the rain measurements; additionally, even the satellites observations, used for comparison, are characterized by large uncertainty to signal ratio, with a not completed estimation of the measurement accuracy. For future developments, rain ground measurements could prove precious for a better data quality characterization (rain gauges or Doppler radar measurements).

2. CAL/VAL MATURITY MATRICES

The following maturity matrix is comprehensive of weather, air quality and precipitation intensity data assessment. The three data batches and relative documentation were separately validated and assessed but the outcome of Cal/Val maturity matrix is the same for three data “projects”. Regarding the validation matrix, three separate outcomes are presented because each assessment is different. The details of the three datasets are separately treated, when needed.

2.1 SUMMARY CAL/VAL MATURITY MATRIX

This assessment aims to review mission quality as evidenced by its documentation. It is divided into the follow sections:

- Product Information
- Metrology
- Product Generation
- Validation Summary

Table 2.1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Data Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed
Product Details	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessable		
Availability & Accessibility	Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Basic		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Geometric Validation Method	Good		
User Documentation	Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Excellent		
	Uncertainty Characterisation AQ and Precipitation data			Not Public
	Ancillary Data			

The atmospheric data assessed in this work are generated by ground-based sensors, the maturity matrix emplaced for atmospheric domain in EDAP+ is intended for satellite acquisitions. In this context, the outcomes of the maturity matrix are obtained slightly changing the rules of applications presented in the atmospheric guidelines, [RD-8] since most of the grading guidelines cannot be applied to ground-based acquisitions (i.e. geometric calibration, geometric processing, mission-

specific processing and the geometric validation). The “geometric” entries of the matrix are not applicable to this assessment, and they are graded as not assessable.

2.1.1 Weather data validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Weather data detailed validation			Key
Measurements		Geometric	
Weather data vs ISD data (weather local network) #1 Method	Weather data vs ISD data (weather local network) #1 Results Compliance	Weather data vs ISD data (weather local network) #1 Method & Results Compliance	Not Assessed
Weather data stations intercomparison #2 Method	Weather data stations intercomparison #2 Results Compliance	Weather data stations intercomparison #2 Method & Results Compliance	Not Assessable
Weather data vs AEMET (local network) daily means #3 Method	Weather data vs AEMET (local network) daily means #3 Results Compliance	Weather data vs AEMET (local network) daily means #3 Method & Results Compliance	Basic
			Good
			Excellent
			Ideal
			Not Public

2.1.2 Air quality data validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Air Quality data detailed validation		
Measurements		Geometric
AQ data vs UK-air data (AQ local network) #1 Method	AQ data vs UK-air data (AQ local network) #1 Results Compliance	AQ data vs UK-air data (AQ local network) #1 Method & Results Compliance
AQ data sensors intercomparison #2 Method	AQ data sensors intercomparison #2 Results Compliance	AQ data sensors intercomparison #2 Method & Results Compliance

Key	
	Not Assessed
	Not Assessable
	Basic
	Good
	Excellent
	Ideal
	Not Public

2.1.3 Precipitation intensity data validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Precipitation intensity data detailed validation		
Measurements		Geometric
Precipitation data vs GPM #1 Method	Precipitation data vs GPM #1 Results Compliance	Precipitation data vs GPM #1 Method & Results Compliance
Precipitation data vs Eumetsat #2 Method	Precipitation data vs Eumetsat #2 Results Compliance	Precipitation data vs Eumetsat #2 Method & Results Compliance

Key	
	Not Assessed
	Not Assessable
	Basic
	Good
	Excellent
	Ideal
	Not Public

2.2 DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	The products are still a test version, and the information is not clearly reported in the user guide. Essential information should be retrieved in presentation materials provided by Vodafone. For the future development of the products, we suggest inserting all the product details in a user guide.
Product Name	Weather, Air Quality and Virtual rain gauges
Sensor Name	Meteorologic data: SENTEC weather stations Air quality data: KUNAK sensors Rain sensor network: Vodafone 5G stations
Sensor Type	Meteorologic data: meteorological sensors Air quality data: air quality sensors Precipitation sensor: mobile communication antennas
Mission Type	Ground sensors network
Mission Orbit	N/A
Product Version Number	Test Version
Product ID	N/A
Processing level of product	Testing Version
Measured Quantity Name	Meteorologic variables: Pressure, Temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction Air Quality data: refer to Table 5.1 Rain sensor network: Precipitation intensity
Measured Quantity Units	Meteorologic variables: hPa, C, %, km/hour, deg from north counterclockwise Air quality data: refer to Table 5.1 Precipitation intensity: mm/hour
Stated Measurement Quality	Not explicitly declared by data provider
Spatial Resolution	Meteorologic data: ground-based measurements Air Quality data: ground-based measurements Precipitation intensity: ground-based measurements. Observations are the results of interaction of transmitted signals along the optical

	<p>path between transmitter and receiver antennas. The distance between these two points is generally between 0.05-degree latitude/longitude as reported in Figure 7-3.</p> <p>Geometrical uncertainties are not provided, but for ground-based observations the coordinates and altitudes are usually measured using GPS positioning. We can suppose that the error is in the order of few tens of meters horizontally and few meters vertically, not impacting atmospheric and rain physical parameters.</p>
Spatial Coverage	<p>The data batch received is part of a larger project called “Network as a sensor” covering several Nations in Europe and Africa as shown in Figure 1-1.</p> <p>Meteorologic data: data batch provided covers the east-coast of Spain and Palma de Mallorca (Balearian island), see Figure 3-1.</p> <p>Air Quality data: data batch provided covers the Glasgow city centre (Scotland, UK), see Figure 5-2.</p> <p>Precipitation intensity: data batch provided covers the south-east coast of Spain, Balearian islands and Spanish Mediterranean Sea. See Figure 7-1.</p>
Temporal Resolution	<p>Meteorologic data: 1 minutes, 5 minutes</p> <p>Air Quality data: 1 minute</p> <p>Precipitation intensity: 15 minutes</p>
Temporal Coverage	<p>2022-today</p> <p>The project starts in 2022 with the deployment of air quality stations in Glasgow (Phase 1). The second phase started in Jun 2023 with the deployment of other Air quality sensors in Spain and Glasgow city. From the received documentation it is not clear if phase 2 comprises the weather stations deployed in Spain.</p> <p>The documentation not clearly indicates the starting point of temporal coverage of meteorologic and precipitation data.</p>
Point of Contact	ilaria.thibault@vodafone.com
Product locator (DOI/URL)	N/A
Conditions for access and use	Access restricted during these testing phases
Limitations on public access	Data still not public
Product Abstract	Weather and air quality data collected via stations installed on the Vodafone’s antennas.

	Precipitation intensity data collected analyzing the perturbation introduced into the signal by the presence of rainfall or snow within the link.
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Availability & Accessibility	
Not Assessable	
Justification	The products are still a test version, data are not distributed to the public.
Compliant with FAIR principles	N/A
Data Management Plan	Not received
Availability Status	Data access is restricted for testing

Product Format, Flags & Metadata	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	Data received are in proprietary format with a minimal set of metadata and flags (quality flags only present for precipitation intensity)
Product File Format	Meteorologic data: JSON format Air Quality data: JSON format Rainfall intensity: CSV format
Metadata Conventions	Not standard
Analysis Ready Data?	Not applicable

User Documentation	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	Public User Guide is not still available during the testing phase, even if basic product information has been delivered. No ATBD delivered; Weather and air quality data are collected via commercial sensors. The measurement characteristics and retrieval algorithm should be obtained from the station's technical specifics.

	Regarding precipitation intensity retrieval no information is available.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>References</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	N/A	N/A
ATBD	N/A	N/A

2.2.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	No information is available regarding the calibration algorithms. Weather and air quality stations calibration could be retrieved from sensors' specifications.
References	N/A

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	This maturity matrix field is referred to satellite missions, so we cannot assign any grade. Vodafone's measurements are collected by ground stations, whose coordinates and altitude are reported in the products. For each precipitation measurement, the coordinates of transmitter and receiver are reported. Geometrical uncertainties are not provided, but for ground-based observations the coordinates and altitudes are usually measured using GPS positioning. We can suppose that the error is in the order of few tens of meters horizontally and few meters vertically, not impacting atmospheric and rain physical parameters.
References	N/A

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	Data received contains some L1 data (Air quality sensors) and information regarding uncertainties in form of precision and accuracy (Weather stations). No traceability chain documented.
References	N/A

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	The calibration algorithm is not provided. We suggest providing the station's technical specifics for weather and air quality data.
References	N/A

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Good – Not Assessable	
Justification	Weather station measurements uncertainty is characterized by the accuracy and resolution values. Proposed grade: Good No uncertainty given for air quality and precipitation intensity data. Proposed grade: not assessable
References	N/A

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	No ancillary data required for measurements.
References	N/A

2.2.3 Product Generation

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	This Maturity matrix field is referred to satellite missions. Ground stations and precipitation intensity measurements are fully localized through the coordinates. In case of precipitation intensity, the coordinates of transmitter and receiver are provided.
References	N/A

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<p>We suggest providing the station's technical specifics and information about the measurement technique.</p> <p>The retrieval algorithm for precipitation intensity measurements has not been provided.</p>
References	N/A

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	<p>No addition processing is required for data.</p> <p>Precipitation intensity data are accompanied by a quality flag. We suggest specifying the classification method if it could be considered a separate process with respect to calibration and retrieval algorithm.</p>
Reference	N/A

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – VODAFONE WEATHER STATIONS DATA (SPAIN)

In this work we examined meteorological stations data from the "Vodafone Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor" initiative, which was set up in several locations. Weather data comprises temperature, pressure, relative humidity, wind speed and direction. We received a data batch from 23 stations located in Spain between 18th of May to 1st of June 2023. The weather sensors are produced by SENTEC, a company that specializes in meteorological sensors [RD-1]. Using the ground network capillarity of Vodafone, the weather stations have been mounted atop towers and antennas to provide meteorological service. Data are cross-referenced with adjacent stations and, when possible, with data from a Spanish meteorological network. The reference data are the global Integrated Surface Database (ISD) [RD-3] and daily means data from the Spanish State Meteorological Agency (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología AEMET) [RD-4]. ISD data are provided by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), that provides measurement of weather combining data from various sources.

The assessment results indicate that the data from the meteorological stations are trustworthy, as their measurements are in line with those of the reference stations, within the margin of error. Statistical evaluations of different sites reveal a positive correlation in the measurements obtained and a high consistency. The meteorological network, which utilizes Vodafone's ground network for weather station installation, offers extensive territorial coverage and holds great potential. This leads to a large amount of meteorological data that could be used to enhance climatological models.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The weather data received consist of 23 stations located in Spain. For the intercomparison exercise we analysed 22 out of 23 weather stations data, since one station is located too far from the other Vodafone stations and from reference local network. The selected Vodafone stations are grouped in areas of about 25-30km radius, and the intercomparison was made between near stations and when possible, with the reference local network (see Figure 3-1 for the weather stations location). The analyses have been performed using 14 days of data, between 18th of May 2023 to 1st of June 2023. Stations are also located in various peculiar environment such as urban, semi-rural and rural environment, according to satellite images.

Figure 3-1 Spain regions with Vodafone weather stations analyzed in this work.

3.2 MEASUREMENTS

3.2.1 Vodafone weather stations measurements and data

Data are received in CSV files (one for each station) that contains the: station code id, datetime (UTC), temperature (°C), pressure, humidity (%), wind direction (degree), wind speed (km/h), state (Spanish county), latitude, longitude, and altitude. The unit of measure is provided for all parameters except for pressure, which is assumed to be (hPa) according to the data range. The provided data are acquired every 1 or 5 minutes. The installed meteorological sensors are from SENTEC [RD-1], whose technical specifications are provided by a table reported in a “Readme” file, that is also reported here in Figure 3-3.

station_id	datetime_utc	temperature_deg	pressure_hpa	humidity_perc	wind_direction_degrees	wind_speed_kmh	state	latitude	longitude	altitude
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:00:00	15.93	985.5	78.67	76.0	7.596	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:05:00	16.02	985.6	77.97	87.0	4.608	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:10:00	16.06	985.7	77.43	94.3	4.068	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:15:00	16.05	985.7	77.03	107.4	6.624	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:20:00	15.95	985.8	77.02	107.7	7.092	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:25:00	15.89	985.8	77.0	107.1	6.408	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:30:00	15.8	985.9	77.25	101.7	10.008	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:35:00	15.68	986.0	78.74	89.8	8.604	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:40:00	15.62	986.0	79.47	120.5	4.932	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:45:00	15.65	986.2	79.7	128.4	2.7	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:50:00	15.65	986.2	80.71	136.3	3.132	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 22:55:00	15.7	986.3	80.44	221.7	1.332	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:00:00	15.75	986.3	79.97	126.5	3.924	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:05:00	15.55	986.4	79.96	305.9	2.268	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:10:00	15.25	986.4	81.5	243.3	2.988	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:15:00	15.2	986.4	81.75	181.7	4.248	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:20:00	15.26	986.4	81.44	109.2	4.608	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:25:00	15.36	986.4	80.8	103.1	5.436	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:30:00	15.19	986.4	81.23	75.8	2.880	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:35:00	14.9	986.5	82.14	77.2	3.456	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:40:00	14.77	986.5	82.57	63.1	4.896	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:45:00	14.95	986.5	81.64	83.3	5.976	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:50:00	14.99	986.5	81.33	103.4	6.228	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-17 23:55:00	15.03	986.4	81.08	66.9	3.06	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-18 00:00:00	15.03	986.4	80.97	96.5	6.768	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-18 00:05:00	15.14	986.5	79.97	130.6	1.548	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-18 00:10:00	14.92	986.6	79.3	225.7	3.168	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0
vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d	2023-05-18 00:15:00	14.71	986.6	79.92	239.4	2.628	Comunidad Valenciana	38.906	-0.421	223.0

Figure 3-2 Data format csv files received for weather stations.

ITEMS	Principle	Range	Resolution	Accuracy
Wind speed	Ultrasonic	0-40m /s	0.01m/s	(0-30m/s)±0.3m/s or ±3% (30-60m/s) ±5%
Wind direction	Ultrasonic	0-360°	0.1°	±3°
Temperature	MEMS	-40 °C - +60 °C	0.01 °C	± 0.3°C (@25°C, typical case)
Humidity	MEMS	0—100%	0.01%RH	±3%RH (0-90%RH)
Atmospheric pressure	MEMS	300 — 1100hPa	0.1hpa	±0.3hpa(0-30°C)
Rainfall	Photology	0-200mm/h	0.2mm	Error<10%

Figure 3-3 Technical specification as range, resolution, and accuracy of the SENTEC Meteorological sensors installed.

3.2.2 Weather stations' location

In this section are reported the details of each location that is analysed in this work. For each location there is a map with distances, the satellite image for details of the area, a table with the corresponding stations id code.

To produce a coherent result, the intercomparison was made with stations that are in the same area within approximately 25-30 km radius. The locations reported in Figure 3-4 are detailed in the following subsections, with dedicated maps and satellite images to visualize the type of location (i.e., urban, semi-rural, rural). The id code of the corresponding station is reported in dedicated tables. The station number reported in tables is related to the station number reported into the map's legend.

3.2.2.1 Palma de Mallorca

Figure 3-4 Vodafone weather stations location and the Integrated Surface Database (ISD) weather station used a reference data for the assessment. The star marker indicates the location of Palma de Mallorca city.

Figure 3-5 Satellite image of the five weather stations located in Palma de Mallorca.

Four stations are in urban area, except Station 1 that is located slightly outside the urban area so it can be categorized as semi-rural area.

Location: Palma de Mallorca	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	Vtg-8584ccc25ac90318
Station 2	Vtg-8584ccc25ac90321
Station 3	Vtg-8584ccc25ac90327
Station 4	Vtg-8584ccc25ac90328
Station 5	Vtg-8584ccc25ac90329

Table 3.2 Identification code of Vodafone’s stations in Palma de Mallorca Island.

3.2.2.2 Cartagena

Four weather stations located in Cartagena, one in urban area (St. 4), two in semi-rural area (St. 2 and 3) and one station that is located outside Cartagena, in semi-rural environment (St.1), see Figure 3-7. The distance between ISD reference station and the Vodafone’s is about 27 km.

Figure 3-6 Map of Vodafone weather stations in Cartagena town and the Surface Database ISD weather station used a reference data for the assessment.

Figure 3-7 Satellite image of the four Vodafone stations located in Cartagena and surrounding area.

Location: Cartagena	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	vtg-8584ccc25ac90333
Station 2	vtg-8584ccc25ac90336
Station 3	vtg-8584ccc25ac90337
Station 4	vtg-8584ccc25ac9033d

Table 3.1 Identification code of Vodafone's stations in Cartagena city.

3.2.2.3 Val D'Albaida

Three weather stations located in the Val D'Albaida area, in the south region of Valencia. The stations are in a similar environment according to satellite images. St.1 and 2 are urban, St.3 is semi-rural.

Figure 3-8 Map of Vodafone weather stations in Val D'Albaida region.

Figure 3-9 Satellite image of the three Vodafone stations located in Val D'Albaida region.

Location: Val D'Albaida	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	vtg-8584ccc25ac90310
Station 2	vtg-8584ccc25ac9032d
Station 3	vtg-8585ccc25ac90306

Table 3.2 Identification code of Vodafone's stations in Val D'Albaida region.

3.2.2.4 Pinet-Barx

The Pinet-Barx location is close to the Val D'Albaida location. In this case the intercomparison was made separately since the Pinet-Barx represent a peculiar rural environment while the Val D'Albaida is more urban/semi-rural environment.

Figure 3-10 Map of Vodafone weather stations located in Pinet-Barx.

Location: Pinet-Barx	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	vtg-8584ccc25ac90326
Station 2	vtg-8585ccc25ac90309
Station 3	vtg-8585ccc25ac9030a
Station 4	vtg-8585ccc25ac9030b

Table 3.3 Identification code of Vodafone's stations in Pinet-Barx area.

Figure 3-11 Zoomed map of Vodafone weather stations In Pinet-Barx. The stations are located in rural area (1 and 2) and in urban area (3 and 4).

Figure 3-12 Satellite image of the four Vodafone stations located in Pinet-Barx area.

3.2.2.5 Val la Vinaxia

Three weather stations located near the Val la Vinaixa, 30km north of Tarragona. The stations are located in a very similar environment according to satellite images (see Figure 3-14), where St.1 is rural area, St.2 is semi-rural, located at 600m from nearest town L'Espluga de Francoli; St.3 is also semi-rural but located at the border of Montblanc town.

Figure 3-13 Map of Vodafone weather stations located in Val la Vinaxia region.

Figure 3-14 Satellite image of the three Vodafone stations located in Val la Vinaxia region.

Location: Val la Vinaxia	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	vtg-8584ccc25ac90330
Station 2	vtg-8584ccc25ac90331
Station 3	vtg-8584ccc25ac90332

Table 3.4 Identification code of Vodafone's stations in Val la Vinaxia region.

3.2.2.6 Nevà/Pardines

Three weather stations located near the border with France, in the North region of Spain. The stations are in mountainous locations, hence the weather variables such as wind speed and direction are expected to be not correlated due to the orography of the region.

Figure 3-15 Map of Vodafone weather stations located in Nevà/Pardines, near the border with France.

Figure 3-16 Satellite image of the three Vodafone stations located near the border with France.

Location: Nevà/Pardines	
Station number	Station code
Station 1	vtg-8584ccc25ac9033a
Station 2	vtg-8584ccc25ac9033b
Station 3	vtg-8584ccc25ac9033c

Table 3.5 Identification code of Vodafone’s stations in Nevà/Pardines area.

3.2.3 Reference data: Integrated Surface Database (ISD) global database from NOAA

To compare the weather stations data provided by Vodafone we used the Integrated Surface Database (ISD). The ISD is a global database comprising hourly and synoptic surface observations compiled from numerous sources into a single common ASCII format and common data model. ISD combines data from more than one hundred original data sources, including numerous data formats that were key-entered from paper forms during the 1950s–1970s time frame. ISD includes a wide range of parameters such as wind speed and direction, wind gust, temperature, dew point, cloud data, sea level pressure, altimeter setting, station pressure, present weather, visibility, precipitation amounts for various time periods, snow depth, and various other elements as observed by each station. The ISD data are downloaded from NOAA database, selecting the region of interest.

The ISD data are provided in CSV format, accompanied by reference documentation [RD-3], [RD-10] and [RD-11]. These data are used to compare the atmospheric parameters measured by weather stations such as temperature, pressure, humidity, wind speed and direction. The ISD data are collected every 30 minutes and the uncertainty is not provided (not in the data, nor in the documentation).

The intercomparison exercise was made for the location of Palma de Mallorca and Cartagena since there is ISD station close to the station under evaluation. Particularly, the distance does not exceed 20 km. For Palma de Mallorca, the average distance ISD- Vodafone’s stations is around 8-12 km and it is considered the best intercomparison in this scenario.

3.2.4 Reference data: Daily average weather data from AEMET

The Spanish State Meteorological Agency (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología AEMET) provides the historical daily, monthly and annual means of weather data from local network (AEMET OpenData). Data comprises Temperature, sea level Pressure, Relative humidity, and Wind Speed (daily means, max and min values), where present. We downloaded the daily means data for the Palma de Mallorca and Cartagena area to provide a comparison exercise [RD-4]. In Palma de Mallorca there are two reference stations located one at the Airport and one at the Harbor. In Cartagena town there is only one reference station. The precise location (latitude, longitude) of stations is not reported; stations are identified by id name (i.e., Palma de Mallorca Aeropuerto, Palma de Mallorca Puerto) or id code (i.e., 7012C Cartagena).

3.3 INTERCOMPARISONS

In this section are reported the intercomparisons of measurements and statistical analysis. The comparison is made with ISD data, between Vodafone's stations and with daily means from AEMET. For each parameter, the correlation coefficient and bias are evaluated matching data measured within the time interval $\pm 15 \text{ min}$. Final considerations of the Vodafone's weather stations are made analyzing the average of statistics parameters obtained for each location.

In the following sections are reported results of selected location cases, for convenience. The statements and considerations are valid for all Vodafone's locations except where expressly stated.

The intercomparison is made for Temperature, Pressure, Wind speed, Wind direction and Relative Humidity collected by sensors. The ISD data does not provide the Relative Humidity but instead the dew point Temperature, from which we retrieved the RH (%) to make a comparison. The algorithm used for the retrieval ([Eq. 3.1] is given by [RD-12].

$$RH \approx 100 - 5(T - T_d) \quad [\text{Eq. 3.1}]$$

In [Eq. 3.1 the quantity T represent the measured temperature by the sensor and T_d the dew point temperature.

The Pressure data reported by Vodafone's is not corrected with the respect of sea level, which is a standard practice for weather data provided from local/global networks. We report the analyses made with the pressure reported in Vodafone data (not corrected) and the sea level pressure retrieved using Eq. 3.2, [RD-13].

$$P_0 = P_1 \left[1 - \frac{0.0065h}{(T + 0.0065h + 273.15)} \right]^{-5.257} \quad [\text{Eq. 3.2}]$$

In Eq. 3.2, P_0 is the mean sea level pressure in hPa, P_1 is the actual measured pressure from station in hPa, T is the temperature in degree Celsius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and h is the elevation of the station in meters (m).

3.3.1 Temperature

In this section the temperature data measured by Vodafone stations are reported, compared with the ISD station when possible. The accuracy of Vodafone's data is $\pm 0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ that is reported on plot with the grey band. Data appears in good agreement with stations located in the same area and with ISD network as well. In Figure 3-17, data from station 1 (purple curve) present few spurious spikes. Data are not accompanied with quality flag, which might help in quality control. In Figure 3-18 are reported temperature data for the Pinet-Barx location. Also, in this case data trend appear in good agreement, stations 1-2 have slightly lower values of temperature that is due to the different location type. Stations 1-2 are in a rural/mountainous area while stations 3 and 4 are at lower elevation and in semi-urban area near the Pinet town, hence the temperature in mountainous location is expected to be lower.

Figure 3-17 Temperature intercomparison between Vodafone’s stations in Palma de Mallorca and the ISD local station situated at the airport of Palma de Mallorca.

Figure 3-18 Intercomparison of temperature values measured by the four Vodafone's station located in Pinet-Barx. Stations 1-2 are in a rural/mountainous area while stations 3 and 4 are at lower elevation and in semi-urban area near the Pinet town, hence the temperature in mountainous location is expected to be lower than semi-urban area.

3.3.2 Pressure

In this section are reported the pressure data (both uncorrected and corrected at sea level) measured by Vodafone stations. Data are compared with the ISD station when possible. The accuracy of Vodafone's station is $\pm 0.3 \text{ hPa}$ for data measured in temperature range (0-30°C). The accuracy is reported on plot with the grey band. The uncorrected values of P present a constant bias with the respect to the ISD reference, but this is due to the non-correction. When data are correct at sea level altitude [RD-13], the negative bias is mostly suppressed. In certain cases, a small bias persists but we think this is due to a wrong attribution of station elevation that might affect the correct evaluation Pressure at sea level. The general trend is in good agreement with the reference.

In Figure 3-19 are reported data compared with the ISD in Cartagena location. Data are uncorrected and the negative bias is evident. station 4 (red curve) present some spurious spikes. Data are not accompanied with quality flag, which might help in quality control. We acknowledge that station 4 present spurious spikes for all measured parameters, hence it is caused by a malfunction of the whole sensor.

In Figure 3-20 is reported the comparison of P at sea level and the bias is strongly reduced.

According to the elevations displayed in Figure 3-21, station 3 and 4 are at placed at the same elevation of about 30 meters. The Pressure at the sea level should be the same but station 4 data appear lower that data of station 3. The elevation associated to the stations might be not accurate, affecting the estimation of Pressure.

Figure 3-22 and Figure 3-23 show the comparison of pressure for the location Val D'Albaida.

Figure 3-19 Pressure (uncorrected) intercomparison between Vodafone's stations in Cartagena and the ISD local station situated at 27km from Cartagena.

Figure 3-20 Intercomparison of sea level pressure values retrieved from the 4 Vodafone's station located in Cartagena.

Figure 3-21 Elevation of the four stations located in Cartagena and the ISD Network station.

Figure 3-22 Pressure (uncorrected) intercomparison between Vodafone’s stations in Val D’Albaida.

Figure 3-23 Intercomparison of sea level pressure values retrieved from the three Vodafone’s station located in Val D’Albaida.

Figure 3-24 Elevation of the three stations located in Val D'Albaida.

3.3.3 Relative Humidity

In this section are reported the Relative Humidity RH measured by Vodafone stations. Data is compared with the ISD station when possible. The RH of ISD network is calculated from dew point and temperature as described in section 3.3. The accuracy of Vodafone's station is $\pm 3\%$ for data in range (0-90%), reported on plot with the grey band. The general trend is in good agreement with the reference and the local variability is due to the different location of the stations.

In Figure 3-25 is reported the RH (%) measured in Palma de Mallorca and compared with the ISD reference. Station 1 (purple curve) present few spurious spikes and ISD as well. Data are not accompanied with quality flag, which might help in quality control.

Figure 3-26 presents the RH data comparison of Val la Vinaixa location.

Figure 3-25 RH intercomparison between Vodafone’s stations in Palma de Mallorca and the ISD local station situated at the airport of Palma de Mallorca.

Figure 3-26 RH intercomparison between Vodafone’s stations in Val la Vinaixa.

3.3.4 Wind Speed and Wind Direction

This section provides the analyses of wind speed and direction. Wind speed and direction are parameters strongly influenced by local orography/morphology [RD-14]. For this reason, we acknowledge that the comparison of measurements produced by sensors placed 10+ km apart is not good condition and the low values of correlation coefficient, and statistical tests does not imply that the sensors are not working properly. The accuracy is $\pm 3^\circ$ for wind direction and for wind speed is $\pm 1 \text{ km/h}$ (0 - 100 km/h). The accuracy of wind speed and direction is not reported on plot to improve data visualization.

Figure 3-27 Wind direction comparison between Vodafone’s stations in Cartagena and the ISD local station.

Figure 3-28 Wind speed measures of Vodafone’s stations in Cartagena.

Figure 3-29 Wind direction comparison between Vodafone's stations in North of Spain (Nevà/Pardines).

Figure 3-30 Wind speed data comparison between Vodafone's stations in Nevà/Pardines location in North of Spain.

3.3.5 Statistical analysis

We apply statistical analyses on data to quantify the variability and intrinsic bias. We evaluate the bias for each measurement (with the respect of reference and between each local station). For each couple station-station we evaluate the average bias and the correlation coefficient (Pearson's correlation coefficient PCC) [RD-15].

For the Palma de Mallorca and Cartagena sites the scatter and qq-plots are evaluated with the respect of ISD reference. The statistical results are all summarized in tables.

Here we show the plots and some results for one selected location.

Figure 3-31 shows the temperature bias evaluated for Vodafone's station in Palma de Mallorca. Table 3.6 summarizes the average bias for each station, the standard deviation associated and the correlation coefficient between temperature measured by the Vodafone n^{th} station and the ISD reference. The average values of correlation coefficients and biases are also listed, accompanied with standard deviation. Table 3.7 presents the NxN correlation coefficient matrix, for temperature parameter, evaluated for each station-station couple located in Palma de Mallorca. The same statistical approach is applied also to pressure Figure 3-32 and Figure 3-33, relative humidity Figure 3-34, wind direction Figure 3-35 and wind speed Figure 3-36. Results are summarized in the following tables.

Table 3.6 Palma de Mallorca statistical analyses of temperature

Vodafone station N°	r Pearson $T_i - T_{ISD}$	Mean ΔT (°C)	dev std Δ
1	0.96	-0.06	0.96
2	0.92	0.53	1.38
3	0.91	0.52	1.39
4	0.91	0.74	1.37
5	0.93	0.40	1.25
	mean value	mean value	mean value
	0.93	0.43	1.27
	dev. std	dev. std	
	0.02	0.27	

Table 3.7 Correlation coefficients between temperature values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

Corr. Coeff. T stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.953976	0.944972	0.952037	0.955962
2	0.953976	1.0000	0.977125	0.989239	0.985578
3	0.944972	0.977125	1.0000	0.974195	0.982045
4	0.952037	0.989239	0.974195	1.0000	0.973707
5	0.955962	0.985578	0.982045	0.973707	1.0000

Figure 3-31 Temperature bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca.

Table 3.8 Palma de Mallorca statistical analyses of pressure (corrected)

Vodafone station N°	r Pearson $P_{sea_i} - P_{ISD}$	Mean ΔP_{sea} (hPa)	dev std Δ
1	0.997	-1.87	0.18
2	0.999	-4.58	0.12
3	0.997	-1.85	0.17
4	0.999	-4.41	0.11
5	0.998	-2.05	0.15
	mean value	mean value	mean value
	0.998	-2.95	0.15
	dev. std	dev. std	
	0.001	1.27	

Table 3.9 Correlation coefficients between pressure (corrected) values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

<i>r</i> Pearson <i>P</i> sea stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.997126	0.994895	0.996599	0.99591
2	0.997126	1.0000	0.998192	0.999446	0.998851
3	0.994895	0.998192	1.0000	0.998166	0.999566
4	0.996599	0.999446	0.998166	1.0000	0.998673
5	0.99591	0.998851	0.999566	0.998673	1.0000

Table 3.10 Correlation coefficients between pressure (uncorrected) values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

<i>r</i> Pearson <i>P</i> uncorrected stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.9964	0.9953	0.9957	0.9947
2	0.9964	1.0000	0.9991	0.9994	0.9990
3	0.9953	0.9991	1.0000	0.9990	0.9996
4	0.9957	0.9994	0.9990	1.0000	0.9989
5	0.9947	0.9990	0.9996	0.9989	1.0000

Figure 3-32 Pressure bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca. For P corrected at sea level.

Figure 3-33 Pressure bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca. For P uncorrected.

Table 3.11 Palma de Mallorca statistical analyses of relative humidity

Vodafone station N°	r Pearson $RH_i - RH_{ISD}$	Mean ΔRH (%)	dev std Δ
1	0.93	-2.52	8.17
2	0.88	-9.12	11.36
3	0.83	-8.65	11.68
4	0.88	-9.31	10.88
5	0.87	-7.96	10.75
	mean value	mean value	mean value
	0.88	-7.51	10.57
	dev. std	dev. std	
	0.03	2.54	

Table 3.12 Correlation coefficients between RH (%) values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

r Pearson RH stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.9214	0.8923	0.9137	0.9205
2	0.9214	1.0000	0.9651	0.9871	0.9813
3	0.8923	0.9651	1.0000	0.9626	0.9744
4	0.9137	0.9871	0.9626	1.0000	0.9709
5	0.9205	0.9813	0.9744	0.9709	1.0000

Figure 3-34 Relative humidity bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca.

Table 3.13 Palma de Mallorca statistical analyses of Wind direction.

Vodafone station N°	r Pearson $Wdir_i - Wdir_{ISD}$	Mean $\Delta Wdir$ (°)	dev std Δ
1	0.49	-5.08	106.84
2	0.38	20.37	119.40
3	0.14	6.37	148.98
4	0.23	32.96	147.94
5	0.16	70.09	152.33
	mean value	mean value	mean value
	0.28	24.94	135.10
	dev. std	dev. std	
	0.13	25.96	

Table 3.14 Correlation coefficients between Wind direction values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

r Pearson Wind dir stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.3453	0.1217	0.2790	0.1952
2	0.3453	1.0000	0.2451	0.3831	0.3370
3	0.1217	0.2451	1.0000	0.2993	0.3740
4	0.2790	0.3831	0.2993	1.0000	0.4834
5	0.1952	0.3370	0.3740	0.4834	1.0000

Figure 3-35 Wind direction bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca.

Table 3.15 Palma de Mallorca statistical analyses of Wind speed

Vodafone station N°	r Pearson $W_{S_i} - W_{S_{ISD}}$	Mean ΔW_s (km/h)	dev std Δ
1	0.67	-4.27	6.08
2	0.55	-4.70	6.94
3	0.56	-6.48	6.83
4	0.57	-3.93	7.20
5	0.65	-3.51	6.31
	mean value	mean value	mean value
	0.60	-4.58	6.67
	dev. std	dev. std	
	0.05	1.03	

Table 3.16 Correlation coefficients between Wind speed values measured from Vodafone stations in Palma de Mallorca.

r Pearson Wind speed stations	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.0000	0.4766	0.3997	0.4881	0.5193
2	0.4766	1.0000	0.3964	0.5130	0.5979
3	0.3997	0.3964	1.0000	0.3952	0.6421
4	0.4881	0.5130	0.3952	1.0000	0.4919
5	0.5193	0.5979	0.6421	0.4919	1.0000

Figure 3-36 Wind speed bias calculated between ISD reference and Vodafone’s station in Palma de Mallorca.

For the correlation coefficients between station-station couples summarized in Table 3.7, Table 3.9, Table 3.10, Table 3.12, Table 3.14 and Table 3.16 we evaluated the average correlation coefficient for each location and for each variable. The results are summarized in Table 3.17.

The average correlation coefficients for each location are remarkably high, with the majority exceeding 0.95. This outcome indicated that the stations are functioning correctly and are appropriately calibrated. Results pertaining to wind direction and speed exhibit lower coefficients, which is expected given that wind measurements are strongly influenced by local conditions.

Table 3.17 Average correlation coefficients for each location and variable.

Location	T	P (uncorrected)	P sea level	RH	Wind dir.	Wind speed
PALMA DE MALLORCA	0.9689	0.9977	0.9977	0.9489	0.3063	0.4920
CARTAGENA	0.7365	0.5087	0.5061	0.7148	0.2045	0.6124
PINET/BARX	0.9603	0.9944	0.9912	0.9464	0.2591	0.4559
NORTH OF SPAIN	0.9533	0.9972	0.9717	0.9574	-0.0755	0.2588
VAL LA VINAIXA	0.9707	0.9967	0.9920	0.9467	0.3413	0.4316
VAL D'ALBAIDA	0.9485	0.9983	0.9977	0.9370	0.4899	-0.1147
AVERAGE TOT	0.918	0.899	0.892	0.903	0.207	0.450
Dev. Std	0.091	0.195	0.193	0.094	0.149	0.114

The results of Cartagena location consistently exhibit lower values compared to other locations. This discrepancy is attributed to the Station 4, where the data display numerous negative spikes, exceeding the instrument's saturation threshold and significantly impacting the overall averages and statistical analyses. The statistics could be enhanced by excluding such values from the analysis. Implementing a data quality control system (quality flag) would effectively mitigate erroneous measurements, thereby improving data quality and statistical robustness.

If the data from these stations were integrated into a meteorological network, they could provide significant value and enhance the quality of meteorological/climatic statistics.

Figure 3-37 Scatter plots for temperature, pressure uncorrected and sea level corrected, Relative Humidity, Wind speed and direction measured at Station 1 of Palma de Mallorca with the respect of ISD network station reference.

For the locations where ISD data reference is available, scatterplots are generated for each variable to visualize the discrepancies with the reference data. Figure 3-37 shows the scatter plots for Station 1 in Palma de Mallorca. Such scatter plots ease the examination of results obtained with correlation coefficients. All parameters can be considered in agreement with the reference data. Note that for pressure, the general trend remains consistent, albeit with a negative shift. This shift is more pronounced for the uncorrected pressure data. When pressure is calculated at sea level, this difference becomes smaller, yet a slight bias persists due to the elevation of the station. The scatter plot for relative humidity (RH) indicates that for values below 40%, the estimation from Vodafone stations tends to be higher than the reference data. This discrepancy may be attributed to the equation used to estimate RH, which may less accurately predict low RH values. The scatter plot of wind direction illustrates it as a purely stochastic variable, dependent on local conditions, and lacking a clear correlation with the reference data, as expected. The same applies for wind speed that exhibits a similar behaviour, showing no distinct correlation with the reference data.

Figure 3-38 QQ-plot evaluated for station 1 of Palma de Mallorca with the respect of the ISD station reference. The QQ-plot is evaluated for all parameters: temperature, pressure, RH, Wind speed and direction.

The QQ-plots between Vodafone’s data and ISD data reference are reported in Figure 3-38. This analysis helps us to check if the two series have a common distribution, through the comparison of quantiles [RD-16]. In the y-axis the values of measurements under test, while the x-axis reports the values of the ISD reference. Temperature presents good agreement with the reference except for values below 15 °C, where Vodafone’s sensors tend to over-estimate the parameter. This principle is equally applicable to Relative Humidity (RH), which is derived from temperature values. The relationship between temperature and RH is linear, as depicted in [Eq. 3.1]. Consequently, the observed overestimation of RH at lower values, relative to the reference, could potentially be attributed to the algorithm employed.

The quantile-quantile plots of pressure reveal a lack of alignment with the trend of the reference. The pressure readings obtained from Vodafone’s sensors consistently fall below the reference, with the divergence amplifying at higher values. While the initial bias can be ascribed to the effect of elevation (see Figure 3-32), the increasing divergence at elevated values may suggest an incorrect calibration of the sensor. The quantile-quantile plots for both wind direction and wind speed clearly indicate that there is no correlation with the reference.

3.3.6 Daily average data intercomparison

In this section the intercomparison of Vodafone’s data with daily averages data from AEMET [RD-4] is reported. The intercomparison is made for the location of Palma de Mallorca and Cartagena.

Figure 3-39 Daily means of Palma de Mallorca site.

Figure 3-39 shows the daily averages of temperature, sea level pressure, relative humidity, and wind speed in Palma de Mallorca location. In Figure 3-40 is reported the comparison of temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed for Cartagena location. The sea level pressure is

not reported on AEMET data for Cartagena town. The coloured bands on plots represents the max and min values (where present) that are used as maximum error. The solid lines are reference data from AEMET, and the circle markers are daily averages evaluated for each Vodafone's station. The general trend of all parameters is in good agreement, as expected. The wind speed is a parameter strongly influenced by local conditions; hence it is expected to present higher variability. The sea level pressure in Figure 3-39 presents the shift between reference data and Vodafone's network, as already highlighted in previous sections. This can be caused by a wrong estimation of elevation that accompanies each station. From Eq. 3.2, an error of 10 m in elevation is equivalent of $\sim 0.6 \text{ hPa}$ pressure variation. In Figure 3-40 the data derived from St. 4 are not reported since that station presented several negative spikes that strongly influence the daily means of all parameters. If quality flags are implemented, they might improve the data quality and provide more accurate data for the final users.

Figure 3-40 Daily means of Cartagena site. The sea level pressure is not reported because AEMET data don't provide it for this site.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the meteorological station data from the "Vodafone Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor" project, which was installed in multiple places throughout Spain. The manufacturer of weather stations is SENTEC [RD-1], specialized in meteorological sensors. The stations have been installed on top of Vodafone towers/antennas, exploiting the Vodafone's ground network capillarity.

We studied the reliability of the data generated by these weather stations. The parameters we examined include **temperature, pressure, relative humidity** of the air, **wind direction**, and **wind speed**. Data was compared with nearby stations and, where possible, with data from a Spanish meteorological network. This comprehensive analysis highlights the project's potential to contribute significantly to climatological modelling/forecasting, while also suggesting strategies to enhance the quality of the data where we think are it necessary. Recommendations

The results obtained clearly indicate that **the meteorological station data are reliable, with measurements aligning with reference stations within the measurement error**. Statistical analyses of various locations point out positive coherence of the obtained measurements and good consistency.

Regarding the analyses of wind direction and speed, one must consider the local and highly variable nature of the parameters under examination. Therefore, the low correlation coefficient values between stations are entirely normal.

The pressure parameter provided is not corrected relative to sea level. Generally, the pressure value in meteorological networks is provided corrected relative to sea level to ensure consistency between measurements obtained at different altitudes. For our analyses, we calculated the correction and compared both the uncorrected pressure and that reported at sea level. The analyses reveal consistent negative bias relative to the reference. These bias decreases when performing the correction to sea level but persists. We believe that this bias may be due to an erroneous evaluation of the station's elevation. Indeed, using to perform the correction, an error of about 10m translates into a pressure difference of approximately 0.6 hPa. *We suggest providing pressure corrected at sea level altitude and accompanied with a more accurate station elevation.*

The provided data do not present any quality control (quality flags). This implies that all data recorded by the sensors in a specific time interval have been delivered without any data check. Some stations present completely unbalanced values, above the instrument's saturation level. These "spikes" significantly influence the statistics, negatively affecting the data quality. In the Cartagena location, station 4 presents several spikes (see Figure 3-19) in all measured parameters between May 19th to May 23rd. As a result, the average values of the correlation coefficient and bias are much lower compared to other locations (Table 3.17). If those values were eliminated, the statistics would return perfectly aligned with the other locations. *We suggest implementing a quality flag system to improve the data information and quality.*

In our view, **this meteorological network holds significant promise** because it makes use of Vodafone ground network for the installation of weather stations, thereby **providing comprehensive territorial coverage**. This results in a substantial volume of meteorological data that could be utilized as input **to improve climatological models** but also **as Cal/Val sites for satellite data**.

5. DETAILED VALIDATION – VODAFONE AIR QUALITY SENSORS DATA (GLASGOW CITY)

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In this work we examined the air quality data from the "Vodafone Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor" initiative, which was set up in Glasgow city centre (Scotland). Air quality data comprises concentration of carbon dioxide (CO_2), nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ozone (O_3), and particulate matter $PM_{1, 2.5, 4, 10}$. We received a data batch from one station located in Glasgow city centre between 18th of May to 1st of June 2023. The Air Quality (AQ) sensors are produced by Kunak air [RD-2], a company that specializes in AQ sensors. Using the ground network capillarity of Vodafone, the weather stations have been mounted atop the Vodafone antenna to provide air AQ service. Data was compared with data from a UK air quality network [RD-5]. The reference data are selected from stations located in Glasgow city centre, close to the Vodafone station.

The assessment results indicate that air quality data present significant enhancements margin. The air quality network holds great potential due to the capillarity of the Vodafone's infrastructure.

5.2 MEASUREMENTS

5.2.1 Vodafone air quality data

In this section, the description of AQ data received is reported, as well as the location of the station and the sensors specification.

We received data from one air quality station located in Glasgow city centre.

The station is made up of multiple sensors that are produced by Kunak company. The list of variables and information received from Vodafone is reported in Table 5.1. Note that this list was received in the form of screenshot attached to a readme file. To improve the reading of this document we decided to transcribe the content of the screenshot in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 List of variables registered by the air quality station. This table is attached at the "readme file" provided by Vodafone.

VARIABLE	VARIABLE NAME	UNITS
AQI	aq_index	-
Battery	battery_voltage	%
Charge	charge_voltage	V
CO2 GC	co2_rel	ppm
CO2 GCc	co2_rel_calibrated	ppm
CO2 GCc AVG1H	co2_rel_calibrated_avg001hh	ppm
CO2 GCc AVG24H	co2_rel_calibrated_avg024hh	ppm
Dew Point	temp_dew_point	°C
Humidity ext	humidity	%
ICharge	charge_int	mA
NO GC	no_rel	ppb
NO GCc	no_rel_calibrated	ppb
NO GCc AVG1H	no_rel_calibrated_avg001hh	ppb
NO2 GC	no2_rel	ppb
NO2 GCc	no2_rel_calibrated	ppb

NO2 GCs AVG1H	no2_rel_calibrated_avg001hh	ppb
NO2 GCs AVG24H	no2_rel_calibrated_avg024hh	ppb
NOx GCc	nox_rel_calibrated	ppb
NOx GCc AVG1H	nox_rel_calibrated_avg001hh	ppb
O3 GC	o3_rel	ppb
O3 GCc	o3_rel_calibrated	ppb
O3 GCc AVG1H	o3_rel_calibrated_avg001hh	ppb
O3 GCc AVG8H	o3_rel_calibrated_avg008hh	ppb
PM-SFR	pm_flow_rate	ml/s
PM1	pm1_calibrated	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM1 AVG1H	pm1_calibrated_avg001hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM1 raw	pm1	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM10	pm10_calibrated	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM10 AVG1H	pm10_calibrated_avg001hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM10 AVG24H	pm10_calibrated_avg024hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM10 Raw	pm10	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM2.5	pm2.5_calibrated	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM2.5 AVG1H	pm2.5_calibrated_avg001hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM2.5 AVG24H	pm2.5_calibrated_avg024hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM2.5 Raw	pm2.5	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM4	pm4_calibrated	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM4 AVG1H	pm4_calibrated_avg001hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
PM4 AVG24H	pm4_calibrated_avg024hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Pressure	pressure	hPa
Signal	signal	dBm
Temp	Sensor temperature	°C
Temp ext	temperature	°C
TPC	pm_count_tot	counts/cm ³
TPC AVG1H	pm_count_avg001hh	counts/cm ³
TSP	pm_quantity_tot	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
TSP AVG1H	pm_quantity_avg001hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
TSP AVG24H	pm_quantity_avg024hh	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

We received a data batch from two sensors (Code id: K-A3 KUNAK 4 and K-A3 KUNAK 2) that we indicated as k2 and k4 in the following analysis. Vodafone does not provide the uncertainty and technical characteristics of sensors. Data provided are both calibrated and non-calibrated, acquired at time resolution of 1 minute over a time period of 14 days (18th of May to 1st of June 2023). The average values over 1, 8 and 24 hours are also given but not for all parameters. The assessment and intercomparison exercise is produced for a selected air quality set of parameters that is possible to compare with other data. Temperature, pressure, humidity profiles, pm counts and flow rate are excluded from this analysis. Figure 5-1 shows the satellite image of Vodafone station location. The station is located on top of a building in urban area close to a park. The Vodafone station is close (less than 600 meters) to two air quality sensors installed by UK-air and use for the intercomparison exercise. The following section gives a comprehensive description of all stations used for the intercomparison and the distances are listed in Table 5.3.

Figure 5-1 Satellite image of Vodafone air quality station location. The orange pointer indicates the Vodafone station, the two yellow pointers represent two air quality sensors used for the intercomparison (Glasgow Townhead GT and Glasgow High Street GHS).

5.2.2 Data reference: UK-air network

The intercomparison exercise of air quality data of Vodafone sensor is made with data from a local network provided by Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs. This local network for air quality monitoring is part of the UK air information resource project [RD-5, RD-17RD-18, RD-18]. From this network we selected 4 stations located in Glasgow city center. The location name and identification code (ID) is reported in

Table 5.2. Data from these stations are not homogenous, not all parameters are given for each station. Data are given as hourly means, the list of parameters is reported in Table 5.4.

Table 5.3 reports all distances between UK-air sensors and the Vodafone station. GT and GHS are the closest to the Vodafone station, within 650 m. The GGWR station is the farthest one (1.7km) and GK station is located near the train station where the data show a more polluted area at 850 m from Vodafone station. In Figure 5-3 is reported the satellite image of GK station. Data were downloaded from the UK-air webpage dedicated, in CSV format. The CSV file also contains pressure, temperature and wind direction that are obtained from external models. Hence, these parameters are not used for the intercomparison. The UK-air data is not accompanied with measurements uncertainties. The reference document [RD-18] reports the UK-air quality network sensors certificate of calibration, released by Ricardo Energy and Environment. It certifies that: *“The reported expanded uncertainties are based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k=2$ providing a level of confidence of approximately 95%. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.”* This

documentation is not produced for the four station used for the intercomparison. We can only assume that the analysis was also produced for the stations listed in

Table 5.2 but the document is not reported on the webpage. Due to the lack of uncertainty information, the plots reported in following sections don't present errorbars.

Figure 5-2 satellite view of air quality sensors placed in Glasgow city. The orange pointer indicates the Vodafone AQ station. The yellow pointers are the UK-air sensors location used for the intercomparison exercise.

Table 5.2 Station name and id code of Glasgow air quality network

STATION NAME	STATION ID	SITE TYPE
Glasgow Great Western Road	GGWR	Urban traffic
Glasgow Kerbside	GK	Urban traffic
Glasgow High Street	GHS	Urban traffic
Glasgow Townhead	GT	Urban Background

Table 5.3: Distances between Vodafone station and UK-air network sensors.

Station-station	distance [m]
Vodafone st.- GGWR	1750
Vodafone st.- GHS	650
Vodafone st.- GK	850
Vodafone st.- GT	383

Figure 5-3 Satellite image of Glasgow Kerbside GK station. The location of GK station appears to be close to the train station. The concentrations of pollutants registered by GK station are higher than the other sensors. Hence, the higher concentration of air quality parameters is due to the location.

Table 5.4 List of air quality parameters measured at every station used for the intercomparison exercise with Vodafone data.

PARAMETERS	STATION ID
<i>NO</i>	GGWR, GHS, GK, GT
<i>NO₂</i>	GGWR, GHS, GK, GT
<i>O₃</i>	GT
<i>PM10</i>	GHS, GT
<i>PM 2.5</i>	GHS, GT

5.3 INTERCOMPARISON

This chapter reports the intercomparison exercises of air quality data. The analyses and comparisons are schematized as follows:

- Calibrated and non-calibrated data comparison from the same sensor.
- Comparison of data measured by k2 and k4 Vodafone sensors (only calibrated data).
- Comparison of Vodafone data with UK-air network sensors.

We decided to follow this approach due to the lack of technical documentation and calibration algorithm. Once we compared the calibrated and non-calibrated data, we selected calibrated data to produce the other intercomparisons. The correlation coefficients and biases are evaluated for each intercomparison. When compared with local network reference, also plots and scatter plots are shown.

5.3.1 Comparison of calibrated and non-calibrated data (from the same sensor)

The Vodafone data batch comprises both calibrated and non-calibrated data for all parameters. The first approach is to plot and compare calibrated and non-calibrated data. We didn't receive technical documentation related to the calibration algorithm emplaced. Hence, the intercomparison can only be qualitative. We notice that the calibrated and non-calibrated data almost overlaps except for negative values in non-calibrated datasets.

Figure 5-4 Calibrated and non-calibrated data comparison measured by sensor K2 on left column and from sensor K4 in right column. The Upper row reports NO concentration comparison, while the bottom row reports the O₃ data comparison.

Figure 5-4 shows the comparison of NO and O₃ calibrated and non-calibrated measured by k2 and k4 sensors. The Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) is 0.9887 for k2 data and 0.9877 for k4 data, underlying that the datasets are very similar. Figure 5-5 reports the differences (bias) calculated between NO cal and NO non-cal. The mean bias is 0.1820 ± 0.7017 [ppb] for k2 data and 0.1866 ± 0.6828 [ppb] for k4 (see Figure 5-5). The mean value of the difference is very close to zero in both cases of NO but also for the other parameters. From these results we derived that there is not a real calibration algorithm applied to data, but data are simply filtered: negative values are replaced with null values. Such a result is also evident comparing numerical values (see Figure 5-6).

Figure 5-5 Bias evaluated between calibrated and non-calibrated datasets of nitric oxide. Left panel shows the results of sensors k2, right panel the results of sensor k4.

Index	Type	Size	Value
17	Float64	1	-0.67
13	Float64	1	-1.83
14	Float64	1	-0.1
15	Float64	1	-1.4
16	Float64	1	-1.88
17	Float64	1	0.02999999999999999
18	Float64	1	0.97
19	Float64	1	-0.82
20	Float64	1	-0.15
21	Float64	1	-0.11999999999999999
22	Float64	1	-0.83
23	Float64	1	-0.3
24	Float64	1	-0.89
25	Float64	1	-0.43
26	Float64	1	-0.55
27	Float64	1	-0.57
28	Float64	1	-0.72

Index	Type	Size	Value
17	Float64	1	0.0
13	Float64	1	0.0
14	Float64	1	0.0
15	Float64	1	0.0
16	Float64	1	0.0
17	Float64	1	0.02999999999999999
18	Float64	1	0.97
19	Float64	1	0.0
20	Float64	1	0.0
21	Float64	1	0.0
22	Float64	1	0.0
23	Float64	1	0.0
24	Float64	1	0.0
25	Float64	1	0.0
26	Float64	1	0.0
27	Float64	1	0.0
28	Float64	1	0.0

Figure 5-6 Numerical data comparison between non-calibrated (left column) and calibrated (right column). Calibrated data are obtained substituting negative values with null values.

5.3.2 Sensor's data comparison (k2-k4 calibrated)

Data received are measured by two sensors (k2 and k4). We first noticed that data length is not equal, the k4 data present 32 elements more than k2. All the elements in k2 are present in k4 data and the sampling interval is in both cases 1 min and 1 sec. We think that 32 elements of k4 are sampled slightly less than 1 min in few cases, generating more data elements. We perform the data comparison measured by the two sensors (only calibrated data) and the correlation coefficient k2-k4 is retrieved for each parameter.

Figure 5-7 Intercomparison of NO concentration measured by Vodafone sensors. The intercomparison is made with calibrated data and the hourly mean concentrations.

Figure 5-8 k2-k4 sensors bias for the NO parameter.

Measurements are in good agreement; the correlation coefficient is above 0.9 for most parameters except for NO_2 , NO_x and O_3 where it ranges between 0.5 and 0.7. The bias for each parameter is also evaluated. Table 5.5 reports the statistical analysis of correlation coefficients and the mean bias accompanied with standard deviation.

Figure 5-9 and Figure 5-10 show NO_x results that produced a correlation coefficient of 0.6081 and mean bias of -1.8309 [ppb]. The results can be compared with data of NO that present a correlation coefficient of 0.9254 and mean bias of 0.4060 [ppb] (see Figure 5-7 and Figure 5-8). Particulate matters all show very good agreements between k2 and k4 sensors, we report the results of one parameter for brevity, Figure 5-11 and Figure 5-12 show the PM1 data.

Figure 5-9 Intercomparison of NO_x concentration measured by Vodafone sensors. The intercomparison is made with calibrated data and the hourly mean concentrations.

Table 5.5 Statistical analysis results for the intercomparison of data measured by k2 and k4 sensor. The second column reports the correlation coefficient evaluated for each parameter. The third and fourth column show the average bias k2-k4 and the associated standard deviation. The units of measurement for bias and associated standard deviation is [ppm] for carbon dioxide, [ppb] for the other oxides and [$\mu g/m^3$] for particulate matters.

Variable (calibrated)	r Pearson sensors k2-k4	Mean bias	Dev std bias
CO_2	0.9484	3.3235 [ppm]	5.7476 [ppm]
NO	0.9256	0.4060 [ppb]	1.6049 [ppb]
NO_2	0.5635	-2.2369 [ppb]	7.5109 [ppb]
NO_x	0.6081	-1.8309 [ppb]	7.8390 [ppb]
O_3	0.5051	0.7389 [ppb]	1.4273 [ppb]
PM 1	0.9906	0.3080 [$\mu g/m^3$]	0.4791 [$\mu g/m^3$]
PM 4	0.9772	0.7596 [$\mu g/m^3$]	1.0887 [$\mu g/m^3$]
PM 10	0.9346	1.0613 [$\mu g/m^3$]	2.6641 [$\mu g/m^3$]
PM 2.5	0.9856	0.5876 [$\mu g/m^3$]	0.7240 [$\mu g/m^3$]

Figure 5-10 k2-k4 sensors bias for the NO_x parameter.

Figure 5-11 Intercomparison of PM_1 concentration measured by Vodafone sensors. The intercomparison is made with calibrated data and the hourly mean concentrations.

Figure 5-12 k2-k4 sensors bias for the *PM1* parameter.

5.3.3 Data comparison with local reference network

The last step of the analysis comprises the intercomparison exercise with local network of air quality stations.

The results from the previous section indicate a negligible discrepancy between the two datasets derived from Vodafone’s sensors. Consequently, we opted to utilize data from sensor k2 for a comparative analysis with the UK-air sensors. The UK-air data are reported as hourly means; thus, we employed the hourly averages of the k2 stations to produce a consistent comparison. The correlation coefficient and the bias analysis are performed. In this case also the scatter plots and qq-plots are provided.

The UK-air sensors do not yield uniform data, with some parameters measured exclusively at specific sites. The comprehensive intercomparison exercise is conducted only for nitric oxide and nitrogen dioxide since the concentrations are measured by all four UK-air sensors. We also compared the PM 2.5 and PM 10 with two UK-air stations and the ozone concentration with only one reference station. The full list of parameters and UK-air sensors ID is summarized in

Table 5.2.

Table 5.6 Statistical results obtained for the comparison of *NO* between Vodafone sensor k2 and UK-air stations. Correlation coefficient, average bias between the two datasets and the associated standard deviation.

parameter: <i>NO</i>	R Pearson	mean bias k2-ref [ppb]	std mean bias [ppb]
GGWR	0.6549	1.076	2.649
GHS	0.655	2.246	2.581
GK	0.2898	-16.403	14.631
GT	0.6334	2.921	2.679

Table 5.7 Statistical results obtained for the comparison of NO_2 between Vodafone sensor k2 and UK-air stations. Correlation coefficient. average bias between the two datasets and the associated standard deviation.

parameter: NO_2	R Pearson	mean bias k2-ref [ppb]	std mean bias [ppb]
GGWR	0.3042	-6.033	6.474
GHS	0.4144	-7.061	5.796
GK	0.3105	-26.609	12.890
GT	0.5428	-3.999	4.793

Table 5.8 Statistical results obtained for the comparison of O_3 between Vodafone sensor k2 and UK-air stations. Correlation coefficient. average bias between the two datasets and the associated standard deviation.

parameter: O_3	R Pearson	mean bias k2-ref [ppb]	std mean bias [ppb]
GT	0.6457	-24.609	12.663

Table 5.9 Statistical results obtained for the comparison of $PM_{2.5}$ between Vodafone sensor k2 and UK-air stations. Correlation coefficient. average bias between the two datasets and the associated standard deviation.

parameter: $PM_{2.5}$	R Pearson	mean bias k2-ref [$\mu g/m^3$]	std mean bias [$\mu g/m^3$]
GHS	0.8043	0.5676	2.1599
GT	0.8463	0.598	1.968

Table 5.10 Statistical results obtained for the comparison of PM_{10} between Vodafone sensor k2 and UK-air stations. Correlation coefficient. average bias between the two datasets and the associated standard deviation.

parameter: PM_{10}	R Pearson	mean bias k2-ref [$\mu g/m^3$]	std mean bias [$\mu g/m^3$]
GHS	0.5909	-1.4496	5.762
GT	0.2634	1.705	13.091

The analysis of the Pearson coefficient reveals a relatively low correlation between the local reference network and the Vodafone's data, with results listed in Table 5.5 - Table 5.10. The intercomparison with GK station exhibits a low correlation and larger discrepancies between datasets. However, these results can be attributed to the GK station is in a more polluted area, as depicted in Figure 5-3, resulting in consistently elevated concentrations compared to other sensors. The discrepancy with data measured at the GT station is reported in the third row of Figure 5-13 (nitric oxide) and Figure 5-15 (nitrogen dioxide). The GGWR sensor is situated 1.7 km away from the Vodafone's sensor, suggesting that the discrepancy could also be addressed to different environments. The GT and GHS are in closest proximity to the Vodafone's station, hence higher data concordance would be expected. The second and fourth row of Figure 5-13 and Figure 5-15

show the intercomparison with GHS and GT sites. The Pearson coefficient reveals relatively low correlation (between 0.41 and 0.65) for NO and NO_2 . The results for particulate matter PM 2.5 present higher agreement with $r > 0.80$ (refer to Figure 5-17. Table 5.9).

Figure 5-13 Nitric oxide intercomparison. Left column shows the data. right column the bias between k2 sensor data and UK-air sensors.

Figure 5-14 Statistical results for Nitric Oxide intercomparison. The left column shows the qq-plots between Vodafone’s data and UK-air reference sensors; the right column reports the scatter plots. The black line on scatter plots represents the ideal trend $x=y$.

Figure 5-15 Nitrogen dioxide intercomparison. The left column shows the data. right column the bias between k2 sensor data and UK-air sensors.

Figure 5-16 Statistical results for Nitrogen Dioxide intercomparison. The left column shows the QQ-plots between Vodafone's data and UK-air reference sensors; the right column reports the scatter plots. The black line on scatter plots represents the ideal trend $x=y$.

Figure 5-17 PM 2.5 data intercomparison. The left column shows the data, the right column the bias between k2 sensor data and UK-air sensors.

Figure 5-18 Statistical results for Particulate matter PM 2.5 data intercomparison. The left column shows the QQ-plots between Vodafone's data and UK-air reference sensors; the right column reports the scatter plots. The black line on scatter plots represents the ideal trend $x=y$.

The statistical analysis of quartiles reported in QQ-plots, and the scatter plots also confirms the previous findings. The QQ-plots are displayed in the left column of Figure 5-14, Figure 5-16 and Figure 5-18. Except for PM 2.5, the intercomparison of nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), and ozone (O_3) reveal a consistent data mismatch. Specifically for nitric oxide, the QQ-plots show that Vodafone's sensors overestimate the measurement compared to the UK-air network (excluding the GT site). Conversely, nitrogen dioxide is consistently underestimated by Vodafone's sensor.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, air quality sensors data from the "Vodafone Air Quality Data, Network as a Sensor" project, were examined. The sensors, produced by KUNAK AIR [RD-2], are installed in Glasgow city centre, on top of Vodafone's infrastructure. We received a data batch from two sensors that are indicated as k2 and k4 in the proposed analysis.

The technical documentation provided is not comprehensive of fundamental information such as sensors' specifications, uncertainties, calibration algorithms, variables description. Due to lack of information the approach for the data assessment is divided into three parts. We first performed the intercomparison exercise between non calibrated and calibrated data measured from the same sensor. This analysis helped us to address the calibration approach applied to data since there is no documentation regarding the calibration algorithm. The second step of the analysis comprises the intercomparison of data measured by the two sensors, k2 and k4, to understand if sensors' specifics are equal, if the two instruments are calibrated or if consistent biases are present. The third part of the work consists in comparing data with local air quality network sensors to assess the reliability of measurements.

Among all the parameters provided in Table 5.4, **we examined** and performed the intercomparison exercise for: **carbon dioxide (CO_2)**, **nitric oxide (NO)**, **nitrogen dioxide (NO_2)**, **nitrogen oxides (NO_x)**, **ozone (O_3)**, and **particulate matter $PM_{1, 2.5, 4, 10}$** .

The analysis of raw and calibrated data suggests that *there is not a real calibration algorithm applied to data but a simple filter that cuts the negative values*. This conclusion is obtained both visualizing data as in Figure 5-4 but also performing numerical data comparison, Figure 5-6. The negative values are simply replaced with zero. *We suggest improving the documentation and data description to simplify data usage but also implementing the calibration algorithm for each atmospheric parameter.*

The intercomparison between the two Vodafone's sensors suggests that *the two sensors produce coherent measurements, with a correlation coefficient above 0.9 in most of the cases and relatively low bias. An exception is given by nitrogen dioxide, nitrogen oxides and ozone, whose correlation coefficient is below 0.6 and with relatively higher bias between k2 and k4 sensors measurements (Table 5.5)*. The discrepancy could be improved if an appropriate calibration algorithm is applied to data. *We suggest providing technical specifications for the installed sensors and the implementation of quality control as quality flags to classify data.*

The last step of the work comprises the intercomparison exercise with external sensors to validate Vodafone's data and assess the consistency of data with the respect of external and certified network sensors. We would expect higher quality from UK-air sensors data since they also lack measurement uncertainties and technical documentation. The presented intercomparison and graphs are missing error-bars, but *the computed bias of Vodafone sensor-UK air sensors might be used as error-bars. The statistical analysis indicates lower correlation between measurements, ($r < 0.8$)*. The scatterplots and the intercomparison of quartiles (QQ-plots) might indicate the presence of systematic errors that can be ascribed to lack of instrument calibration.

The results highlight that *the meteorological data is reliable, with measurements aligning with reference stations within the measurement error*. Statistical analyses of various locations indicate a positive coherence of the obtained measurements and good consistency.

In our view, **Vodafone's air quality sensors are promising ground network that can provide capillary atmospheric data**, leveraging on Vodafone's facilities infrastructure. We are aware that the data batch analyzed is part of a pilot project. Whether the proposed revisions are implemented, the quality of data and the project itself would be significantly improved.

7. DETAILED VALIDATION – VODAFONE PRECIPITATION INTENSITY RETRIEVAL FROM WIRELESS LINKS (SPANISH EAST COAST AREA)

7.1 Introduction

Vodafone rain data is collected measuring the differences introduced in a signal by the transmission process between two points on the ground. This measurement technique could produce a huge amount of data, due to the capillary diffusion of antennas to collect mobile signals, and not present the difficulties presented in the satellite measurements.

To explore the potentiality of Vodafone rain dataset, we analysed the data from May 17th to June 2nd, 2023, collected in the east coast of Spain. The measurements are comprised between 37 and 43 deg latitude and -2 and 5 deg longitude. Figure 7-1 shows satellite view of the east coast of Spain.

Figure 7-1 Region selected for the intercomparison.

7.2 MEASUREMENTS

7.2.1 Vodafone rain rate measurements

The dataset received and analysed in this study is composed of more than 8.2 million observations, focused on the coast and on the Balears islands. A quality flag is employed to characterize the data quality. In the absence of more detailed information on how the flag is assigned, we decided to employ for this study only the data flagged with High quality, resulting in 3.6 million observations

after the screening. Statistical analysis has been conducted using also mid-quality observations and the obtained results are similar to those presented in this work.

The larger part of the dataset is composed of no-rain measurement (rain intensity equal to 0), with just 3.9% of the observations reporting a positive rain intensity value. The rain intensity histogram is reported in Figure 7-2 in which the non-zero observations only are represented for clarity.

Figure 7-2 Rain intensity histogram. Only the non-zero observations have been represented.

Figure 7-3 Distance between transmitter and receiver histogram. The Y axis represents the occurrence of a certain distance value, high and medium quality observations.

Due to the nature of Vodafone measurement technique, it is not possible to assign univocally a couple of coordinates to the observations; each measurement is correlated to two couples of coordinates belonging to the two points from which the signal is transmitted and received. The precipitation intensity should be treated as the result of the interaction of the signal during the entire optical path (link) between the transmitter and the receiver. As shown by Figure 7-3, almost the totality of the dataset is composed of links within 0.1 deg for both latitude and longitude (~10km), and about 95% of the total within 0.05 deg (~5 km); this histogram has been calculated including both High and Medium quality measurements. High quality observations are entirely within 0.025 deg (~2.5 km) of distance, as reported in Figure 7-4.

Figure 7-4 Distance between transmitter and receiver histogram, high quality observations only.

Figure 7-5 reports the daily number of measurements, while Figure 7-6 the daily mean of the precipitation intensity, calculated on the entire intercomparison region. The 24th and 26th of May are characterized by stronger precipitations.

Figure 7-5 Daily number of measurements.

Figure 7-6 Daily mean rain intensity calculated on the entire intercomparison region.

We did not find ground datasets available in the intercomparison region that could provide a statistically significant amount of data, for this reason we decided to compare Vodafone dataset to the reference satellites. Vodafone data have been intercompared with GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly 0.1 x 0.1 deg V07 (hereinafter GPM, [RD-19]) and with EUMETSAT H60 product [RD-7], EUM hereinafter.

7.2.2 Reference data: GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 v07

GPM dataset is composed by satellites observation from different platforms, employing both infrared and microwave measurements, with a spatial resolution of [0.1x0.1] deg (latitude/longitude) and a time resolution of 30 minutes. Figure 7-7 shows the average map of precipitation intensity during the intercomparison period.

Figure 7-7 GPM time averaged precipitation intensity on the intercomparison area.

For the intercomparison we couple each pixel of the GPM maps with the average of all Vodafone measurements within that pixel within a maximum temporal distance of ± 15 minutes. As can be seen from Figure 7-3, the distance between the transmitter and the receiver of an observation is generally smaller than the horizontal resolution of the reference dataset (0.1 deg), with the 95% of the dataset within 0.05 deg. For this reason, in the coupling process, we decided to consider each measurement as a point observation and assign to it the coordinates of the mid-point between transmitter and receiver positions. Together with the average value, we calculate for each pixel at each time the standard deviation, the minimum and maximum value, and the number of observations. We decided to not use the standard deviation as an estimation of Vodafone uncertainty, given the non-gaussian distribution of the measurements, as can be seen in Figure 7-2. The stochastic nature of the precipitation events does not provide a clear interpretation of the standard deviation parameter as uncertainty estimator.

The GPM dataset presents a quality flag indicating also the instruments used for the measurement (*precipitationQualityIndex* in the product). All the examined data are marked with the value 0, indicating lower quality observations from infrared observations. Considering this, no screening has been applied on these reference data.

The dataset has a low signal to noise ratio, given to the large value of random error, as discussed in the [RD-7]. The random error variable in the files is *randomError*; a scatterplot between reference measurements and random error is represented in Figure 7-8. The random error has values larger than the measurements; the reference ATBD [RD-20] introduce the random error as an estimation of the uncertainty for the measurements that need to be improved (page 30) with the measurements bias not estimated. The random error represents an underestimation of the total uncertainty of GPM, however, in absence of a better estimation we will use it as the total uncertainty of the reference. Given the statistical nature of this error (considerable as noise), when an average operation will be performed on an ensemble of reference measurements, the uncertainty of the mean will be considered as the mean uncertainty divided by the square root of the number of measurements (error on the mean).

$$\sigma_{mean} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{\sum_i \sigma_i}{N}$$

Figure 7-8 Scatterplot between GPM measurements and uncertainty.

7.2.3 Reference data: EUMETSAT Final Precipitation L3 v07 (H60)

EUM dataset is composed of observations with an average spatial resolution of 0.041 x 0.037 deg in latitude/longitude and a time resolution of 15 minutes (a finer scale with respect to GPM). Even for EUM the Vodafone observations belonging to a certain pixel (in space and time) have been averaged together to have the co-located Vodafone values for the comparison. EUM uncertainty is not included in the dataset, so we decided to not consider it in the comparison [RD-21].

EUM time averaged map is reported in Figure 7-9. With respect to GPM the rain precipitation is higher, especially in the south.

Figure 7-9 EUMETSAT time averaged precipitation intensity on the intercomparison area.

The study will often present the difference between measurements, together with the difference uncertainty: the difference uncertainty will be equal to the reference uncertainty, given the lack of uncertainty value for Vodafone data.

In the comparison we can also define the difference (Δ) uncertainty (σ) ratio:

$$\mu = \Delta/\sigma$$

A difference will be called significant when the absolute value of μ will be larger than 1. The results of the intercomparison will be presented in the next paragraph.

7.3 INTERCOMPARISON

7.3.1 Vodafone vs GPM all measurements

In this paragraph we will present the average maps of the observations of the two datasets, considering all measurements, including for both datasets measurements on which no precipitation is revealed.

The precipitation intensity map, averaged on the entire intercomparison period is presented in Figure 7-10 and Figure 7-11 for Vodafone data and GPM, respectively. Both datasets reveal a greater concentration of rain in the southern area, near the Spanish city of Murcia and a drier area in the north and in the Maiorca Island. The two datasets differ on Ibiza Island, where the Vodafone data show less precipitation with respect to satellite data.

The difference between these two maps is shown in Figure 7-12; the average spatial difference is 0.00 mm/h with a standard deviation of 0.19 mm/h. Maximum and minimum value of 2.43 and -0.62 mm/h respectively are reached on the south continental coast and on Ibiza Island.

Figure 7-10 Vodafone precipitation map (time averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-11 GPM precipitation map (time averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-12 Vodafone vs GPM spatial difference (averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-13 GPM mean uncertainty.

Figure 7-13 represents the uncertainty for the time averaged precipitation; the large number of observations averaged together led to a relatively small uncertainty assigned to each pixel. Figure 7-14 displays GPM random error, as reported in the product files and time averaged on the intercomparison period. As can be noted the reference measurements are characterized by a low signal to noise ratio; low precision measurements are a characteristic of satellite rain measurements, especially on infrared spectrum such as the reference observations.

Figure 7-14 GPM random error time averaged.

In this part of the work the reference signal to noise ratio and delta to noise ratio will not be shown due to the presence of many no-rain observations that would introduce many zero values on the averages, not allowing for a correct representation.

Figure 7-15 Ratio between difference and uncertainty map.

Figure 7-16 Vodafone and GPM timeseries averaged on the intercomparison region.

Figure 7-15 shows the ratio between difference and uncertainty map (μ), averaged in time. The average operations reduce the effect of the random noise and generate small uncertainty, resulting in μ values lower than one.

Figure 7-16 displays the time series of the measurement couples, spatially averaged on the intercomparison region with the shaded area as the mean uncertainty of the reference dataset. The time series have a correlation coefficient of 0.79, a mean difference of -0.03 mm/h with a standard deviation of 0.20 mm/h, a mean uncertainty of 0.07 mm/h and a mean random noise of 1.15 mm/h.

7.3.2 Vodafone vs GPM rain measurements only

We decide to select and compare the measurements characterized by precipitation intensity greater than zero for at least one of the two Vodafone and reference datasets, to correctly make a correct analysis to the Vodafone datasets. This avoids inserting bias in the statistics due to the no-rain observations.

We will define **rain measurements** as those which have a non-zero value, while **clear measurements** the others.

For a total number of observations equal to 206924, Vodafone rain measurements represent 7%, while GPM rain measurements are 16% of the total. Table 7.1 reports the four cases on which we have rain in both datasets, just for one of them and clear in both datasets. There is a considerable number of observations on which Vodafone does not measure any precipitation while satellite presents rain measurements (11%). The opposite situation, in which Vodafone make a clear measurement while GPM a rain one, occurs on just 2% of the total. Our analysis includes these two situations, together with the rain-rain case, for a total of 38073 couples, 18% of the total.

Figure 7-17 Vodafone precipitation map, only rain measurement included. (averaged on the intercomparison period).

Figure 7-18 GPM precipitation map, only rain measurement included. (averaged on the intercomparison period).

Table 7.1 Rain measurements (single datasets and coupled datasets).

	Clear	Rain
Vodafone	191536 (93%)	15388 (7%)
GPM	173602 (84%)	33322 (16%)
	GPM clear	GPM rain
Vodafone clear	168851 (82%)	22685 (11%)
Vodafone rain	4751 (2%)	10637 (5%)

Figure 7-17 and Figure 7-18 show Vodafone and GPM maps time averaged and composed using just rain measurements. Even this subset shows the greater precipitation intensity on the south coast and larger differences on Ibiza Island and on the central coast; the map differences is in Figure 7-19.

The average uncertainty is reported in Figure 7-20; the mean operation led to a reduction of the noise and leads to a relatively small values of uncertainty. The average random error map for rain measurements is represented in Figure 7-21; as reported by Figure 7-8 the random error increase for heavier precipitations.

Figure 7-19 Vodafone vs GPM difference (rain measurements).

Figure 7-20 GPM uncertainty (time averaged)

Figure 7-21 GPM random error time averaged, rain measurement only.

Figure 7-22 Ratio between difference and uncertainty averaged on time (rain measurements only).

Figure 7-22 presents the ratio μ for rain measurements only. Values are generally lower than 1, with some pixels presenting significant differences.

Table 7.2 reports the statistics regarding the spatial analysis for both all measurements and rain measurements datasets.

Table 7.2 Spatial difference statistics

Spatial difference statistics	All measurements	Rain measurements
Bias [mm/h]	-0.03	-0.18
Difference std dev [mm/h]	0.18	0.77
Max difference [mm/h]	2.51	8.48
Min difference [mm/h]	-0.39	-1.60
Mean uncertainty [mm/h]	0.04	0.49
Mean random noise [mm/h]	1.14	5.16
Mean μ	0.15	0.77

Figure 7-23 Timeseries of rain measurements only, averaged on the intercomparison area.

Figure 7-23 represents the time series of rain measurements, averaged on the entire intercomparison area. The shaded area is the calculated uncertainty on the time averages of GPM. Table 7.3 reports the statistics for the time series with all measurements and rain measurements. Rain measurements are characterized by greater variability, less correlation (0.50) and a larger random noise of GPM.

Table 7.3 Timeseries statistics

Time series statistics	All measurements	Rain measurements
Correlation coefficient	0.79	0.50
Mean difference	-0.03 mm/h	-0.20 mm/h
Difference std dev	0.20 mm/h	0.77 mm/h
Mean uncertainty	0.07 mm/h	0.26 mm/h
Mean random noise	1.15 mm/h	4.46 mm/h
Average μ	0.12	0.67

Figure 7-24 Reports the average differences for all measurements and for rain selection, with the uncertainty on the mean difference presented as shaded area.

Figure 7-24 Average difference vs time calculated for all measurements and rain measurements.

7.3.3 Statistical analysis

In this paragraph we will present the statistical results obtained comparing the couples of co-located Vodafone and GPM measurements.

Figure 7-25 Vodafone vs GPM scatter-plot.

Figure 7-25 shows the scatterplot between GPM and Vodafone. Given the high number of couples taken into consideration we opted for a density map representation, in which the colours represent the base-10 logarithm of the number of couples for a certain pixel. The regions in the space of measurements without a couple of observations are not coloured, while the areas with larger density are in red and smaller densities in blue. The fit results are 0.63 slope and 0.23 mm/h of intercept, with a correlation coefficient equal to 0.32 and an RMS of 3.02. However, the couples do not appear to follow a linear relation and tend to concentrate in the region characterized by precipitation intensity less than 5 mm/h. This tendency is confirmed by the low value of correlation coefficient obtained. These results are not surprising, given the stochastic and local nature of precipitation, as confirmed by literature. The fit results are also affected by the fraction of couples on which GPM does not measure any precipitation, while Vodafone present a rain measurement.

The mean bias calculated is -0.18 mm/h with a standard deviation of 3.08 mm/h and an average random error equal to 5.18 mm/h, as reported in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4 Vodafone vs GPM statistics.

Vodafone vs GPM	
Number of couples (rain)	38073
Fit slope	0.63
Fit intercept	0.23 mm/h
Correlation Coefficient	0.32
Bias Mean value	-0.18 mm/h
Bias Standard deviation	3.08 mm/h
Mean random error	5.18 mm/h

Figure 7-26 Vodafone vs GPM measurement histogram.

Figure 7-27 Histogram of differences for both all measurements and rain measurements.

Figure 7-28 Histogram of differences in term of relative occurrence; particular of the rain distribution.

Figure 7-26 reports the measurement histogram in log scale; Vodafone distribution present less observations with precipitation intensity below 6 mm/h while a greater number above this threshold (bins width 0.33 mm/h).

Figure 7-29 Mean difference as function of GPM precipitation intensity and number of couples for each bin (bin width equal to 1 mm/h, rain measurements only).

Figure 7-27 and Figure 7-28 show the distribution of the differences; the rain distribution presents a peak at -0.3 mm/h and a second peak at 0.0 mm/h. Such results reveal an underestimation of Vodafone with respect to GPM.

Figure 7-29 displays the average difference, standard difference, and number of couples as function of GPM precipitation intensity. These parameters have been calculated dividing the GPM datasets into bins of 1 mm/h. The purple curve is the average of the difference Vodafone – GPM for that bin, the shaded area represents the standard difference, and the orange curve (right y axis) is the number of couples within each bin. The calculation has been done using the rain measurements only. The bias is within -1.8 mm/h up to 6 mm/h of GPM measurement; after this threshold we observe some oscillation due to the smaller number of measurements for each bin and the uncertainty characterizing the heavier rain, with a tendency of more pronounce bias values affecting the intense precipitations.

Figure 7-30 shows the histogram of μ ratios. The distribution appears centred on -0.17 within the non-significative differences area [-1, 1] with the right tail more extended than the left tail. The reader should consider the fact that the uncertainty of the single couple is equal to the random noise of GPM, so it has a low signal to noise ratio, differently from the spatial and temporal averages shown in the previous paragraph, on which the average operation reduces the uncertainty.

Figure 7-30 μ histogram (rain measurements only).

7.3.4 Vodafone vs EUM all measurements

As for GPM, this first exercise will be conducted considering all measurements together, including for both datasets measurements on which no precipitation is revealed.

The precipitation intensity map, averaged on the entire intercomparison period is presented in Figure 7-31 and Figure 7-32 for Vodafone data and Eumetsat respectively. The reader should note the smaller pixels due to finer scale of Eumetsat data.

As for GPM, both datasets reveal a greater concentration of rain in the southern area, near the Spanish city of Murcia and a drier area in the north and in the Maiorca Island, with the precipitation of Eumetsat larger than Vodafone and GPM values. The difference between these two maps is shown in Figure 7-33; the average spatial difference is -0.17 mm/h with a standard deviation of 0.17 mm/h. Maximum and minimum value of 1.48 and -1.03 mm/h. The average difference is negative and more pronounced with respect to GPM case.

Figure 7-34 shows the time series of the measurement couples, spatially averaged on the intercomparison region. The time series have a correlation coefficient of 0.67, a mean difference of -0.17 mm/h with a standard deviation of 0.45 mm/h.

Figure 7-31 Vodafone precipitation map (time averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-32 Eumetsat precipitation map (time averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-33 Vodafone vs Eumetsat spatial difference (averaged on the entire intercomparison period).

Figure 7-34 Vodafone and Eumetsat timeseries averaged on the intercomparison region.

7.3.5 Vodafone vs Eumetsat rain measurements only

We selected and compared the measurements characterized by a precipitation intensity greater than zero for at least one of the two Vodafone and reference datasets. We remember that for rain measurements we refer to those which have a non-zero value, while clear measurements the others.

Figure 7-35 Vodafone precipitation map, only rain measurement included. (averaged on the intercomparison period).

Figure 7-36 Eumetsat precipitation map, only rain measurement included. (averaged on the intercomparison period).

On a total number of observations equal to 767109, Vodafone rain measurements represent 4%, while Eumetsat rain measurements are 16% of the total. Table 7.1 reports the four cases on which we have rain in both datasets, just for one of them and clear in both datasets. Results are similar

to those observed for GPM; there is a considerable number of observations on which Vodafone does not measure any precipitation while satellite presents a rain measurement (16%), while the opposite situation, on which Vodafone make a clear measurement while Eumetsat a rain one, occurs on just 1% of the total. These two situations will be included in our analysis, together with the rain-rain case, for a total of 156707 couples, 20% of the total.

Table 7.5 Rain measurements (single datasets and coupled datasets).

	Clear	Rain
Vodafone	734525 (96%)	32584 (4%)
Eumetsat	173602 (84%)	33322 (16%)
	Eumetsat clear	Eumetsat rain
Vodafone clear	610402 (80%)	124123 (16%)
Vodafone rain	8323 (1%)	24261 (3%)

Figure 7-35 and Figure 7-36 show Vodafone and Eumetsat maps time averaged and composed using just rain measurements. There are remarkable differences in the south and north area, while the difference is reduced in the central part of the coast.

Figure 7-37 Vodafone vs Eumetsat difference (rain measurements).

Table 7.6 reports the statistics regarding the spatial analysis for both all measurements and rain measurements datasets.

Table 7.6 Spatial difference statistics.

Spatial difference statistics	All measurements	Rain measurements
Bias [mm/h]	-0.17	-0.77
Difference std dev [mm/h]	0.17	0.64
Max difference [mm/h]	1.48	5.56
Min difference [mm/h]	-1.03	-2.24

Figure 7-38 Timeseries of rain measurements only, averaged on the intercomparison area.

Figure 7-38 represents the time series of rain measurements, averaged on the entire intercomparison area. The statistics for the time series with all measurements and rain measurements are reported in Table 7.7. Figure 7-39 reports the average differences for all measurements and for rain selection.

Table 7.7 Timeseries statistics.

Time series statistics	All measurements	Rain measurements
Correlation coefficient	0.67	0.26
Mean difference	-0.17 mm/h	-0.35 mm/h
Difference std dev	0.45 mm/h	1.64 mm/h

Figure 7-39 Average difference vs time calculated for all measurements and rain measurements.

7.3.6 Statistical analysis

In this paragraph we will present the statistical results obtained comparing the couples of collocated Vodafone and Eumetsat measurements.

Figure 7-40 Vodafone vs Eumetsat scatterplot.

Figure 7-40 shows the scatterplot between Eumetsat and Vodafone. Given the high number of couples taken into consideration we opted for a density map representation, in which the colors

represent the base ten logarithm of the number of couples for a certain pixel. The regions in the space of measurements without a couple of observations are not coloured, while the areas with larger density are in red and smaller densities in blue. The fit results are 0.32 slope and 0.26 mm/h of intercept, with a correlation coefficient equal to 0.26 and an RMS of 3.51. The couples do not appear to follow a linear relation and tend to concentrate in the region characterized by lower precipitation intensity as for GPM case. This tendency is confirmed by the low value of correlation coefficient obtained. As considered for GPM, this kind of analysis is strongly affected by the local and stochastic nature of precipitation. The mean bias calculated is -0.83 mm/h with a standard deviation of 4.04 mm/h, as reported in Table 7.8.

Table 7.8 Vodafone vs Eumetsat statistics.

Vodafone vs Eumetsat	
Number of couples (rain)	156707
Fit slope	0.32
Fit intercept	0.26 mm/h
Correlation Coefficient	0.26
Bias Mean value	-0.83 mm/h
Bias Standard deviation	4.04 mm/h

Figure 7-41 Vodafone vs Eumetsat measurement histogram.

Figure 7-42 Histogram of differences for both all measurements and rain measurements.

Figure 7-43 Histogram of differences in term of relative occurrence; particular of the rain distribution.

Figure 7-41 reports the measurement histogram in log scale; Vodafone distribution present less observations with precipitation intensity below 17 mm/h while a greater number above this threshold (bins width 0.33 mm/h).

Figure 7-44 Mean difference as function of GPM precipitation intensity and number of couples for each bin (bin width equal to 1 mm/h, rain measurements only).

Figure 7-42 and Figure 7-43 show the distribution of the differences; the rain distribution presents a peak at 0.0 mm/h with the left tail more populated. These plots reveal an underestimation of Vodafone with respect to Eumetsat.

Figure 7-44 displays the average difference, standard difference, and number of couples as function of Eumetsat precipitation intensity. These parameters have been calculated dividing the Eumetsat datasets into bins of 1 mm/h. The green curve is the average of the difference Vodafone – Eumetsat for that bin, the shaded area represents the standard difference, and the orange curve (right y axis) is the number of couples within each bin. The calculation has been done using the rain measurements only. The bias is negative, more pronounced for heavier precipitations.

8. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Vodafone precipitation intensity data has been assessed with two reference satellites, GPM and Eumetsat. The methodology of the intercomparison for both satellites has been judged as “Good”.

The measurements uncertainty of both references is difficult to evaluate, as reported in their documentations: GPM report just an estimation of the random error, while Eumetsat does not include any uncertainty value in the product.

The intercomparison has been conducted on the east Spain, region characterized by different weather conditions during intercomparison period, from clear sky to heavy rain, which could be considered a good representation of the typical weather conditions of Europe during late spring.

Satellite observations, especially on the infrared band, are typically more representative of the precipitation at the top of the clouds, while it is more difficult to establish the rain amount reaching the surface. The ideal reference for Vodafone measurements would be ground stations or geo-radar observations but they were not available for the region and period studied.

The Geometric assessment methodology and results have been judged as “Not Assessable”. Vodafone data should be considered as ground measurements, even if they are composed by a transmitter and a receiver station, generally within 5 km of distance for high quality flag. Satellites observations appear not to be an adequate solution for geometric assessment, while it should be conducted using ground stations.

Assessment result have been judged “Basic” for both references. A general agreement within Vodafone and GPM/Eumetsat can be observed averaging the results on the entire intercomparison region or observing the average time series. However, the single couple comparison, analysed with the scatterplot and histograms, produces low values of correlations. A negative bias also emerges with respect to the references, characterizing especially heavier rains.

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